

Structural and adsorption properties of Areca husk carbon synthesized by physical, chemical and microwave activation methods

Hemashree K., Chaithra P. and J. Ishwara Bhat*

Department of Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199, Karnataka, India

E-mail : bhatij@yahoo.com

Manuscript received online 22 January 2016, accepted 25 April 2016

Abstract : Synthesis of activated carbon from Areca husk has been carried out by three different methods namely physical, chemical ($ZnCl_2$) and microwave activation and characterized by XRD, FTIR, SEM, TGA, Elemental analysis etc. XRD results reveal that the chemically activated carbon is more amorphous in nature compared to the other two synthesized carbons. The SEM images reveal the presence of large number of pores or active centers created on the surface as a result of activation. TGA data indicates the synthesized carbons to be thermally more stable than Areca husk. These synthesized carbons were used for the removal of maleic acid. The effect of acid concentration, contact time, temperature and adsorbent dosage has been studied and the adsorption data were fitted to Freundlich, Langmuir and BET isotherms. The rate of adsorption was determined by using the first and second order kinetic models. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated by analyzing the effect of temperature on the adsorption process. Among the three synthesized carbons, the chemically activated carbon was found to be more effective for the removal of maleic acid.

Keywords : Areca husk, activated carbon, characterization, maleic acid, adsorption.

Introduction

Activated carbon is a form of carbon which is used as an adsorbent in various industrial processes^{1,2}. The adsorbing capacity is due to its extended surface area and highly developed porosity. These properties are very useful for the removal of toxic materials, organic and inorganic components, acids, metal ions etc. from aqueous solutions. Effluents from various industries contain such toxic materials which can be removed easily by the use of activated carbon. However, commercially available activated carbon is quite expensive and hence activated carbon derived from agricultural waste materials becomes a good replacement in this sense. Several reports exist in literature on the synthesis of low-cost activated carbons and their applications in the removal of dyes, acids, metal ions, organic and inorganic materials etc.³⁻⁸.

This paper reports the synthesis of activated carbon from Areca husk by three methods, namely, physical, chemical and microwave activation which are designated as PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC respectively and the application of these carbons on the adsorption of maleic

acid. The effect of acid concentration, contact time, temperature and adsorbent dosage has been reported. The adsorption data were fitted to Freundlich, Langmuir and BET isotherm. The rate of adsorption was determined from the first and second order kinetic models. Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH , ΔS and ΔG were calculated by analyzing the effect of temperature on the adsorption process.

Results and discussion

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The synthesized activated carbons were subjected to powder X-ray diffraction studies and resulted diffractogram is shown in Fig. 1 which was used to evaluate interplanar distance (d), miller indices (hkl) and cell parameter (a) etc. As shown in Table 1, the presence of highly intensified and less intensified peaks in X-ray spectrum indicates the presence of both crystalline and amorphous types of carbons in the synthesized carbons. From the Fig. 1 and Table 1, it is clear that the CAHC is more amorphous in nature compared to PAHC or MWAHC. Decrease in in-

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC.

Table 1. XRD data of PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC

Sample	2 θ	Intensity	d	hkl	a
PAHC	21.8	409	4.08	100	4.08
	28.5	632	3.13	110	4.43
	40.6	324	2.22	111	3.85
	48.0	141	1.89	210	4.23
CAHC	11.5	344	7.69	100	7.69
	25.2	503	3.53	210	7.90
	28.4	409	3.14	211	7.70
	33.1	301	2.70	220	7.65
	36.4	264	2.46	310	7.80
	38.1	221	2.36	311	7.83
MWAHC	41.2	261	2.19	222	7.59
	18.06	266	4.91	100	4.91
	28.28	498	3.15	110	4.46
	29.72	255	3.00	111	5.20
	40.50	270	2.22	210	4.98
	44.56	141	2.03	211	4.98

tensity of the peaks at a particular 2θ angle for all the three carbons is in the order PAHC > MWAHC > CAHC indicates transformation from crystalline to amorphous form of carbons. All the three carbons show similar value for cell parameter, a , indicating the cubic crystal struc-

ture of the synthesized carbons. The cell volume varies in the order of PAHC < MWAHC < CAHC as expected.

The crystallite size (D) was determined by using Debye-Scherrer equation¹³ and the crystallinity index (CrI) was calculated¹⁴ to know the degree of crystallinity in PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC. The crystallite sizes (1.4316 Å, 1.4218 Å and 1.4309 Å) and crystallinity indices (58.54, 27.63 and 51.20) were obtained for PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC respectively. Hence the inference is PAHC is more crystalline in nature because of the higher crystallinity index, which is supported by the lower cell volume and larger crystallite size. Amorphous nature of CAHC may be confirmed by the lower crystallinity index, larger cell volume and smaller crystallite size. This varies in the order PAHC > MWAHC > CAHC probably due to the treatment process involved. $ZnCl_2$ used in the activation of CAHC react with the raw material and this made the obtained activated carbon to show amorphous nature. These differences in the crystallinity of three types of activated carbons affected the surface functionality and also surface morphology which are identified in IR spectrum and SEM analysis.

Scanning Electron Microscopic analysis :

SEM images of all the three activated carbons were obtained and are shown in Fig. 2. The SEM micrographs clearly show the presence of large number of pores or active centers on the surface and are different from those reported images⁸. This may be due to the variation in the environment and the nutrients put to the plant during its growth.

PAHC shows layer like surface with strong and thick pore walls. Fig. 2b shows SEM micrographs of CAHC. The $ZnCl_2$ used not only acted as activating agent during the course of the reaction, but also acted as dehydrating agent. It got hydrated by absorbing water molecules and gets dehydrated on heating leading to the creation of pores as shown in Fig. 2b probably $ZnCl_2$ treated system is more non-crystalline in nature. This concept is also supported by XRD patterns shown in Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of MWAHC (Fig. 2c) shows some shrinkage of the surface. Probably, the microwave radiation has made the

Fig. 2. Scanning Electron Micrographs of (a) PAHC, (b) CAHC and (c) MWAHC.

size of the pores to shrink in comparison with other two cases.

FT-IR spectral analysis :

The FTIR spectra of AHR and three types of synthesized activated carbons were recorded and are displayed in Fig. 3a. and 3b respectively. The functional groups related to the spectral peaks are listed in Table 2a and 2b. O-H stretching vibration is observed in the case of AHR, but not in the case of synthesized carbons, probably due to loss of water molecule during heating process or due to the chemical interaction of $ZnCl_2$ with water molecules as

Fig. 3a. FTIR spectrum of AHR.

Fig. 3b. FTIR spectra of synthesized carbons.

which is confirmed by XRD analysis also. A broad peak in the range $3600-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed in the case of PAHC and CAHC which may be due to trace of left over adsorbed moisture on the surface of synthesized activated carbons.

It is a known fact that Areca husk is mainly composed of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin¹⁵. The proposed mechanism of degradation of cellulose by the action of $ZnCl_2$ has been reported¹⁶. A notable decrease in intensity of C-O stretching vibration in CAHC confirms this reaction. A significant decrease in the intensity of C=O

Table 2a. Functional groups of AHR

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group assignment	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group assignment
3392	Intermolecular H-bonded O-H stretching	1376	C-H bending (symmetric) of methyl group
2920	C-H stretching of alkanes	1320	C-H in-plane bending
1654	C=O stretching (shifted to lower wavenumber may be due to resonance)	1265	C-H in-plane bending
1516	Aromatic C=C stretching	1159	C-O stretching of tertiary alcohol
1458	C-H bending of methylene group	1107	C-O stretching of secondary alcohol
1427	C-H bending (asymmetric) of methyl group	1037	C-O stretching of primary alcohol
		896, 601	C-H out-of-plane bending

Table 2b. Functional groups of three types of activated carbons

Wavenumber region (cm ⁻¹)	PAHC	CAHC	MWAHC	Functional groups
1750–1650	1710	–	1665	C=O stretching
1600–1475	1584	1572	1584, 1484	Aromatic C=C stretching
1450–1350	1371	1365	1390	C-H bending of methyl group
1300–1000	1252	1200	1193	C-H in-plane bending
1260–1000	1110	1114	1116	C-O stretching of secondary alcohol
900–690	757	777	975, 798	C-H out-of-plane bending

stretching vibration in PAHC and MWAHC and absence of C=O stretching in CAHC indicates the likely release of CO during the formation of activated carbons by thermal decomposition.

Nagaraja *et al.*¹⁵ have reported 0.60% of nitrogen in Areca husk. But the qualitative test carried out for nitrogen in the case of AHR did not show even the traces of it indicating the absence of amide C=O or C-N group stretching.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermal behavior of AHR, PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC is shown in the Fig. 4. AHR shows a three-step thermogram, wherein at the first stage ≈12% weight loss occurs in the temperature range 50–100 °C which can be attributed to loss of moisture contained the sample. The major weight loss takes place in the second step within the temperature range of 220–350 °C which is attributed to the decomposition of hemicellulose and cellulose³. Lig-

Fig. 4. Thermograms of AHR, PAHC, ZAHC and MWAHC.

nin also starts to decompose at this temperature range, but the major decomposition of lignin takes place in the temperature range 420–480 °C³.

The thermograms of PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC show only two degradation steps. The initial weight loss which occurs at a temperature < 110 °C is due to the loss of trace amount of moisture content. But here, as is evident from the Fig. 4, the loss in weight due to moisture content is low compared to AHR because of the lesser moisture content in the synthesized AC. The presence of small amount of moisture content is reflected in FTIR spectra also, by the appearance of broad peak in the range 3600–3000 cm⁻¹. The major weight loss occurs in the temperature range 350–650 °C. Since PAHC and CAHC were synthesized at 300 °C, below which the hemicelluloses and majority of cellulose are decomposed, the major weight loss in these carbons should be due to the

decomposition of lignin. The decomposition rate was smaller in case of synthesized activated carbons as compared to AHR indicating the fact that synthesized carbons are thermally more stable than AHR. Weight loss is directly related to the stability of the system. Therefore synthesized carbons are more stable than AHR.

Elemental analysis :

The elements present in PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC are given in Table 3. All the three carbons show higher concentration of Na and K compared to rest of the elements. This may be due to the areca absorbed soil content. Elements such as Cu, Cr, Fe and Ni appeared in smaller quantity in all the three carbons probably due to the soil content absorbed by areca. Higher amount of lead may be due to added potash (locally called as ash) to the soil for the growth of areca plant.

Electrochemical properties :

The conductivity of CAHC (0.052 mS) is found to be higher compared to that of PAHC and MWAHC (0.029 and 0.033 mS respectively). The higher conductivity of CAHC may be attributed to the ions produced as a result of interaction of surface hydroxyl groups with ZnCl₂. There was no notable change in pH of the synthesized carbons. It was comparable with that of water (6.79).

Adsorption studies :

Effect of acid concentration :

Adsorption experiments were carried out with different initial concentrations of acid in the range 0.02–0.1 N. The amount of acid adsorbed increases with increase in acid concentration.

Adsorption isotherms : The process of adsorption was studied by fitting the adsorption data into three well known isotherms namely Freundlich, Langmuir and BET.

Freundlich adsorption isotherm is given by

$$\log q_e = \log k + \frac{1}{n} \log c_e \tag{3}$$

where q_e is the amount of acid adsorbed, c_e is the concentration of acid, k and n are constants depending upon the nature of adsorbate and adsorbent. The values of n and k were calculated respectively from the slope and intercept of the linear plot between $\log q_e$ and $\log c_e$ (Fig. 5a) and are given in Table 4.

Langmuir isotherm assumes the formation of monolayer coverage of adsorbent surface by the adsorbate molecules. Langmuir adsorption isotherm is given by

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{bq_m} + \frac{C_e}{q_m} \tag{4}$$

where q_e is the amount of acid adsorbed at a given concentration of acid C_e , q_m is the maximum amount adsorbed in forming a complete monolayer, b is the Langmuir constant. The Langmuir constant, b and q_m were determined from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of C_e/q_e versus C_e (Fig. 5b), and are given in Table 4. From the Fig. 5a and 5b, it is clear that both the Freundlich and Langmuir models hold good in the case of adsorption of maleic acid onto PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC.

The nature of adsorption can be investigated from the separation factor (R_L)³.

$$R_L = \frac{1}{(1 + bC_0)} \tag{5}$$

where b is the Langmuir constant and C_0 is the initial acid concentration. The value of R_L determines the nature of adsorption to be irreversible ($R_L = 0$), favorable

Table 3. Elemental composition of different carbons

Sample	Concentration of elements (ppm)							
	Cu	Cr	Fe	Ni	Pb	Na	K	% of OC
PAHC	0.130	0.391	0.220	0.175	1.215	3.7	81.0	18.60
CAHC	0.089	0.228	0.173	0.168	0.882	1.0	1.8	18.75
MWAHC	0.113	0.163	0.221	0.123	0.802	3.9	80.0	23.70

Table 4. Isotherm parameters for the adsorption of maleic acid on PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC

Sample	Freundlich model		Langmuir model		
	n	k	b	q_m	R_L
PAHC	8.197	0.083	210.40	0.064	0.04–0.18
CAHC	4.273	0.145	99.380	0.088	0.17–0.49
MWAHC	5.714	0.066	119.33	0.0465	0.07–0.26

($0 < R_L < 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$) or unfavorable ($R_L > 1$). The R_L value obtained in the present case lies in the range 0–0.5 for all the three synthesized carbons indicating the favorable adsorption.

BET isotherm assumes the formation of multilayer of adsorbed molecules at the surface of adsorbent. BET adsorption isotherm equation is given by

$$\frac{C_e}{(C_s - C_e)q_e} = \frac{1}{K_b q_m} + \left(\frac{K_b - 1}{K_b q_m}\right)\left(\frac{C_e}{C_s}\right) \quad (6)$$

where C_e is concentration of dye in solution, C_s denotes the saturation concentration of the dye, q_e is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbate, q_m is the amount of dye adsorbed in forming a complete monolayer. K_b is a constant which is obtained from the intercept of the linear

plot of $\left(\frac{C_e}{C_s - C_e}\right)\frac{1}{q_e}$ versus $\frac{C_e}{C_s}$.

Fig. 5c shows that the adsorption data does not satisfy the linear form of BET isotherm for the whole range of acid concentration indicating that adsorbed molecules does not form multilayer on the surface of adsorbent. Application of BET equation on limited ranges of concentration indicates the formation of multilayer and later desorption of adsorbed layers may results in non-linearity of the plot as observed in Fig. 5c. Hence it may be concluded that the adsorption of maleic acid follows Langmuir model where only the monolayer of adsorption is taking place.

Effect of contact time :

Effect of contact time on the adsorption of maleic acid onto CAHC, PAHC and MWAHC were studied by taking a known concentration of acid (0.04 N) for different time intervals in the range 15–90 min. The rate of ad-

Fig. 5. (a) Freundlich isotherm, (b) Langmuir isotherm and (c) BET isotherm.

sorption is higher in the initial stages and gradually decreases with time. CAHC has higher adsorption capacity compared to PAHC and MWAHC (Fig. 6).

Adsorption kinetics : Kinetics of adsorption were stu-

Fig. 6. Effect of contact time on the adsorption of maleic acid.

died by considering two well known models namely first and second order kinetic models.

The integral form of first order kinetic equation is given by³

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad (7)$$

where q_t is the amount of acid adsorbed at time t , q_e is the amount adsorbed at equilibrium and k_1 is the first order rate constant.

Second order kinetic model is represented by the equation

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (8)$$

where k_2 is the second order rate constant.

The applicability of first and second order kinetic models were tested by plotting $\log (q_e - q_t)$ vs t and t/q_t vs t respectively. The values of rate constants and q_e are given in Table 5. The second order kinetic model gives better R^2 value (0.998–0.993) compared to first order kinetic model (R^2 value lies in the range 0.980–0.941) and also the value of q_e obtained is in agreement with the theoretical value. Hence it can be concluded that the second order kinetic model (Fig. 7) fits better than that of

Table 5. Kinetic parameters of adsorption of maleic acid

Sample	First order		Second order	
	k_1	q_e	k_2	q_e
PAHC	0.039	0.034	1.500	0.061
CAHC	0.020	0.021	1.790	0.084
MWAHC	0.030	0.021	2.000	0.046

Fig. 7. Second order kinetic model for the adsorption of maleic acid on PAHC, CAHC and MWAHC.

first order for the adsorption of maleic acid onto CAHC, PAHC and MWAHC.

Effect of temperature :

Effect of temperature on the adsorption of maleic acid was studied by taking a known concentration of acid (0.04 N) at different temperatures in the range 288–343 K (Fig. 8). Even though the temperature coefficient for the adsorption is low, an increase in the acid uptake was observed with increase in temperature. Hence the adsorption of maleic acid onto CAHC, PAHC and MWAHC can be said to be endothermic.

Thermodynamic parameters of adsorption : Thermodynamic parameters namely change in enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) can be obtained from van't Hoff equation (eq. (9)) and from the values of which the change in free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) of adsorption can be determined (eq. (10)).

$$\ln K = \frac{-\Delta H^\ddagger}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{R} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger \quad (10)$$

where K_c is the equilibrium constant which is obtained as $K_c = q_e/C_e$. The ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were obtained from the slope and intercept of the plot of $\ln K_c$ vs $1/T$. The values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are given in Table 6.

Fig. 8. van't Hoff plot for the adsorption of maleic acid.

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of maleic acid

Sample	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
PAHC	3.410	13.8	-0.916
CAHC	2.404	13.5	-1.821
MWAHC	1.862	10.0	-1.198

The change in enthalpy, ΔH^\ddagger , is found to be positive indicating the endothermic nature of adsorption of maleic acid on the synthesized carbons. Further the negative values of ΔG^\ddagger indicate the spontaneity of adsorption of maleic acid. Positive value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates the decrease in the stability of adsorbed layers on the surface which is reflected in BET plot by the non-linearity of the plot.

Effect of adsorbent dosage :

The rate of adsorption increases with increasing the adsorbent dosage. This is because on increasing the amount of carbon the number of active centers available for adsorption increases which results in increased adsorption.

The variation in the % removal of acid with the increase in adsorbent dosage is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Effect of adsorbent dosage on the adsorption of maleic acid.

Materials and methods :

Areca husk (AHR) from dried areca nut was collected from nearby village. Ripen red colored areca was dried under sunlight for 40 days. Then the husk was peeled off. It was washed several times with distilled water to remove dust particles and adhered impurities on the surface. Then it was dried in the oven at 100 °C and crushed into small pieces.

Maleic acid was obtained from Finar Chemicals Limited, Ahmedabad, India. Distilled water was used for the preparation of maleic acid solution.

Preparation of activated carbon :

Activated carbons were synthesized from dried Areca husk by physical activation¹ (at 300 °C for 2 h), chemical activation with $ZnCl_2$ ⁹ (at 300 °C for 2 h) and microwave activation¹⁰ (at 70 W of power for 90 min).

Characterization techniques :

X-Ray diffraction studies were performed with Rigaku Miniflex 600 (Japan) for 2θ values 10° to 50° at 40 kV and 15 mA using $CuK\alpha$ radiation. IR spectra were recorded using IR Prestige-21 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer, Shimadzu (Japan) in the wave number range 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Scanning electron micrographs were re-

recorded using Sigma series Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (Ziess). Thermogravimetric analysis was done by using the instrument SDT Q600 V20.9 (Japan). The samples were heated from room temperature to 800 °C, under nitrogen atmosphere, at a rate of 10 °C/min. Elemental analysis was carried out by using GBC (Australia) Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, Model No. GBC 932 plus and the Flame photometer 130 (Systronics, India). The solution was prepared as reported¹¹. The organic carbon content in the activated carbon was determined by Walkley and Black method¹².

Adsorption studies :

All the three types of activated carbons were subjected to acid adsorption studies with different concentrations of maleic acid. 500 mg of activated carbon was transferred to different stoppered bottles and stirred with different concentrations of maleic acid for 30 min and filtered. The filtrate was analyzed to get the concentration of acid after adsorption. The amount of acid adsorbed was calculated using the relation

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \times M \times V}{W} \quad (1)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and final concentration of acid (N), M is the equivalent weight of acid; V is the volume of acid (L) and W is the amount of carbon (g).

Adsorption kinetics were studied by taking a known concentration of maleic acid and stirred with 500 mg of carbon for different time intervals. Similarly the effect of temperature also studied by performing the adsorption experiment at 288, 303, 318 and 343 K.

Conclusion

Activated carbon was prepared from Areca husk by physical, chemical ($ZnCl_2$) and microwave activation methods and are subjected to various characterization techniques such as XRD, FTIR, SEM, TGA *etc.* to analyze the nature of synthesized carbons. The synthesized carbons show both crystalline and amorphous nature and the crystal system was found to be cubic based on XRD data.

SEM results showed the presence of large number of active centers on the surface of the synthesized carbons. The TGA indicated the synthesized carbons are thermally stable compared to AHR. The adsorption capacity of these synthesized carbons was examined by the adsorption of maleic acid and the adsorption data were well fitted to Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. The adsorption kinetics followed second order kinetic model. The thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger were determined and the process of adsorption of maleic acid was found to be endothermic and spontaneous. Among the three synthesized carbons, CAHC was found to be more effective for the adsorption of maleic acid.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Coordinator, DST-FIST Programme, USIC, DST-PURSE, Mangalore University for providing instrumental facilities. The authors are also thankful to UGC-SAP, Delhi for past-financial assistance to carry out the present research work. One of the authors, Hemashree K., is thankful to Department of Science and Technology, Government of India for providing financial support through INSPIRE programme.

References

1. Teresa J. Bandoz, "Activated Carbon Surfaces in Environmental Remediation", Vol. 7, Interface Science and Technology, Netherland, 2006.
2. Roop Chand Bansal and Meenakshi Goyal, "Activated Carbon Adsorption", CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, 2005.
3. Maedeh Mohammadi, A. J. Hassani, Abdul Rahman Mohamed and G. D. Najafpour, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2010, **55**, 5777.
4. Xincheng Lu, Jianchun Jiang, Kang Sun, Xiping Xie and Yiming Hu, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2012, **258**, 8247.
5. Y. C. Sharma, Uma and F. Gode, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2010, **55**, 3991.
6. N. V. Sych, S. I. Trofymenko, O. I. PoddubnayaI, M. M. Tsyba, V. I. Sapsay and D. O. Klymchuk, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2012, **261**, 75.
7. Y. C. Sharma, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2011, **56**, 478.
8. A. Basker, P. S. Syed Shabudeen and P. Vignesh Kumar, *Int. J. ChemTech. Res.*, 2014, **6**, 1309.
9. S. Karthikeyan and P. Sivakumar, *J. Environ. Nanotechnol.*, 2012, **1**, 05.

10. Justyna Kazmierczak-Razna, Piotr Nowicki and Robert Pietrzak, *Powder Technol.*, 2015, **273**, 71.
11. M. Turoti and E. Bello, *World Rural Observ.*, 2013, **5**, 64.
12. A. Walkley and I. A. Black, *Soil Sci.*, 1934, **37**, 29.
13. Devarly Prahaz, Y. Kartika, N. Indraswati and S. Ismadji, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2008, **140**, 32.
14. Guanfeng Lin, Jianchun Jiang, Kaijin Wu and Kang Sun, *Bioenergy Res.*, 2013, **6**, 1237.
15. R. Nagaraja, B. R. Gurumurthy and M. B. Shivanna, *IMPACT : Int. J. Res. Appl. Natural and Social Sci.*, 2014, **2**, 105.
16. A. S. Amarasekara and C. C. Ebede, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2009, **100**, 5301.